

Fe- and Zn-biochar mediated carbamazepine removal via heterogeneous Fenton process

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INTRODUCTION

Carbamazepine (CBZ) is classified as a persistent organic pollutant, because its removal efficiency in water treatment plants is about 10%.

The Fenton process is one of the most effective advanced oxidation processes and is used to treat water with a high content of complex organic matter, as well as other non biodegradable compounds.

Increasing attention is focused on the use of biochar as a catalyst in order to use sewage sludge as a resource, not the waste. Due to its low cost, large specific surface area and good stability, biochar is a promising material that can be compared with other carbon materials. It has been often applied as carrier to improve the performance of iron and other ions impregnated in the carbon matrix.

In this work, the removal of carbamazepine was performed using the Fenton process catalyzed by modified biochars, Fe-BC and Zn-BC. The test included the synthesis of biochar and the optimization of the conditions for the degradation of CBZ, using the Fenton process, with varying doses of hydrogen peroxide, CBZ and prepared catalysts, as well as pH and reaction time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the synthesis of biochar, the final sludge from the wastewater treatment plant in the settlement of Kovilj (near Novi Sad), Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia was used.

The biochar preparation procedure - Chen et al. (2020). Impregnation with iron and Zn onto biochar - (Iurascu et al., 2009; Azmi et al., 2014). Specific surface area was determined by A BET analyzer .

To optimize the process conditions, Definitive screening design (DSD), was assessed in order to achieve the maximum efficiency of the applied treatment and the degradation of the selected pollutant.

The tests were carried out on JAR test apparatus. The absorbance (A) was measured at a wavelength of CBZ $\lambda_{max} = 285$ nm. Toxicity of samples was tested with the *Aliivibrio fischeri* bacteria bioluminescence test. The mineralization of effluents was determined using TOC analyzer

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The impregnation of the pristine biochar with Fe (III) (BET= 3.807 m²/g) and precipitation with Zn (II) ions (BET= 104.7 m²/g) influenced the increase of the specific surface areas of the pristine material (BET= 57.83 m²/g). The basic scheme of the experiment, obtained by applying the DSD model with 5 numerical factors, consists of 12 experiments and 2 central points (Table 1).

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Table 1. Matrix of experiment with achieved CBZ removal efficiencies

Sample	Removal efficiency (%)	
	Fe-BC	Zn-BC
1	78	79
2	87	85
3	88	58
4	84	79
5	1	81
6	88	85
7	83	87
8	7	90
9	0.2	95
10	79	85
11	79	88
12	88	93
13	96	96
14	96	98

The results of testing the efficiency of the Fenton process in the removal of carbamazepine are shown in Table 4, where the range of removal efficiency was established from 0.2% to 96% for Fe-BC, from 58% to 98% for the Zn-BC catalyst.

The statistical model within the Fenton process for:

1. Fe-BC suggests a high carbamazepine removal efficiency of 95.885% under the following optimal conditions: pH=5.5, [CBZ]=5.5 mg/l, [Fe-BC]= 60 mg/l, [H₂O₂]= 10.5 mM, t=105 min.
2. Zn-BC suggests a high carbamazepine removal efficiency of 97.09% under the following optimal conditions: pH=5.5, [CBZ]=5.5 mg/l, [Zn-BC]= 60 mg/l, [H₂O₂]= 10.5 mM, while the reaction time is not proposed by the model, assuming that it does not have a large effect on the efficiency

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that both biochars showed good catalytic performance under the applied conditions of the Fenton process. Toxicity measurements showed high inhibition percent (~85%) in both cases, pointing out on formation of toxic intermediates after Fenton reaction of 105 minutes. Further investigation will be conducted for longer reaction time, aiming on decreasing the effluent toxicity. Also, significant mineralization, measured as TOC, was achieved (~80%). The next step that will be implemented is the characterization of the obtained effluents after the optimal conditions using ultra-performance liquid chromatography (UPLC)-high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) method.

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